

Research Impact in Focus: Tools and Strategies for Promotion and Tenure Documentation

● Prepared by Max Liboiron for the IndigeLab Network, 2025

Introduction

This guide offers practical advice and examples for identifying measures and metrics that can help demonstrate the impact of your research in a promotion and tenure file. There is no single or universal way to capture research impact—what counts as meaningful will vary by discipline, methodology, audience, and goals. This resource is not a checklist of requirements, but a collection of strategies to help you make your contributions legible and compelling to reviewers across different contexts. It's based on experience as a committee member, external reviewer, and specialist in the politics of quantitative methods.

Principles of using measures and metrics to demonstrate impact

- **Curate**, don't stuff. This list is a buffet of different tools to show various forms of impact. Use this toolkit to curate—not stuff—the most convincing types of impact that best fit your case (see Henville 2020 on why more is not better).
- There should be a **clear line** between your institution's criteria for promotion and tenure, your work and its goals, and the impact metric(s).
- Always use **both quantitative and qualitative** forms of evidence.
- Numbers never speak for themselves. **Contextualize** what the number means.
- Always include the **source** of your data and the date it was generated to maintain transparency.
- **Define** your measures and metrics. Each metric privileges some types of outputs, impacts, and disciplines over others.
- **Be consistent** with measures and metrics you use. Don't use Publonscore for some papers and Altmetrics for others (or if you do, provide a compelling explanation for why you are using apples and oranges to evaluate the same thing)
- Use a **range of impact measures** to show the same impact from different perspectives, or multiple impacts of the same project.
- **Take time** to explore which measures and metrics best represent your type of research.

Framing

Many scholars—rightfully—approach quantitative measures with caution, given the power dynamics, exclusions, and simplifications often embedded in them. But these politics are not fixed. You have some agency in how your work is framed and understood, and measures (observations) and metrics (calculations) can be used on your own terms to highlight the kinds of impact that matter to you. When aligned with your theory of change—how you believe research contributes to social, political, ethical, or environmental transformation—these tools can help make your contributions legible to others while also offering new insights into your own work. For example, when I graphed my research outputs by type (peer-reviewed articles, blog posts, reports, op-eds), I noticed a growing diversity over time. That visualization revealed how I was evolving as a scholar and writer in ways I hadn't fully seen before.

If you don't curate the quantitative methods to characterize your research, evaluators will do it for you. Exercise your agency, expertise, and politics so that the way your research impacts are framed best aligns with the spirit of your work.

Prepare

There are some things you can do to ensure your that your research outputs are more easily picked up by bibliometrics software. Get and use an ORCID identification when you publish, which is especially important if your name changes or your name is common. Make a Google Scholar and/or Web of Science researcher profile and clean up any duplicate or missing research outputs. If you produce a lot of reports, datasets, policy briefs, or other outputs that aren't peer reviewed articles, use a service that gives them DOIs like Crossref or DataCite, or repositories like Zendo.

Bibliographic metrics and services for publications

H-index

There is a lot of critiques about the h-index (Hirsch index), including that it replicates gender and age biases as well as biases within disciplines (e.g. Bastian et al. 2017). If your university allows it, you may want to skip the H-index altogether. If so, directly quote the university document that lets you avoid it, since external reviewers may expect it and even cast doubt if it's absent.

There are, however, a few ways to use the h-index that might benefit you:

- Google Scholars h-index includes grey literature like reports and op eds.
- You can compare your own h-index from different times in your career. H-graphs by Google Scholar chart your h-index over time.
- You can compare your h-index against the average in your field, as different disciplines and sub-fields have different indices. If you are using an H-index, always include information about the benchmarks in your sub-field, which committees and reviewers may not know.
- You can use research detailing why h-indexes are biased to argue for not using them, when appropriate
- Consider using Author Field Weighted Citation Impact (FWCI) and/or Article Field Weighted Citation Impact, both of which account for context better than h-index. However, be sure to explain how these metrics are calculated since many reviewers will not be familiar and may not trust an unknown metric (see [Chivers et al., 2023](#)). You may want to use FWCI in combination with the H-index.
- Different repositories will give you different h-indices, mainly because the index calculation includes the number of your articles and the number of citations per article, and repositories have more or less complete records of each, depending on discipline and other factors. Check out a few to make sure you have the most complete record. Some of the software listed below calculate h-indices.

Scopus and Web of Science

SCOPUS and Web of Science are both citation databases of peer-reviewed research, each with a slightly different disciplinary focus. Your university library will almost certainly have access to both. Use them to search your name in Research profiles to see your h-index, co-author lists, citation reports, disciplines you publish in, Author Impact Beamplot Summary (WoS), map of who is citing you based on home institutions, your reviews, patent citations, and more. You can create a reviewer profile and correct results, add alerts, and more.

Patent metrics from the Derwent Innovations Index

2 Sum of Times Cited by Patents

2 Citing Patents

Subject category breakdown of the citing patents from the Derwent Innovations Index:

Web of Science analysis of the disciplines that cite a patent held by the author. This can help make arguments about interdisciplinary impacts, and impacts on innovation. It can do the same disciplinary analysis for journals and citations.

Geographic Citation Map

The citation map shows the distribution of the researcher's citations across the globe:

- For each article in the Web of Science Core Collection that cited the researcher's work, a city with a contributing author's institution represents a data point
- A publication may appear under multiple locations if the contributing authors are affiliated with different institutions
- The number of data points on the map may be higher than the sum of times cited in the Web of Science Core Collection

Blue circles can be clicked to zoom in and see more precise locations, red pins can be clicked to see the details of papers citing the researcher's work from a particular city.

The citation map may take a while to load if there are more than 1,000 citations.

Author Impact Beamplot

Range: Recent 10 Years

Open Filters >

Two bibliometrics from Web of Science. The top shows a map of where the author is cited (based on the home institutions of first authors citing the text). The bottom is an impact beamplot, which “shows the volume and citation impact of an individual’s publication portfolio through time. [Unlike h-index] It is also not necessarily biased against individuals who have taken a career break or published less at any given time” (Szomszor 2021).

OpenAlex

OpenAlex is an open-access catalogue that indexes scholarly work, from articles to datasets to reviews to book chapters. They have a more extensive extra coverage of humanities, non-English languages, and the Global South. You can search for your name, institution, and coined phrases and it captures a wide range of research outputs and creates some basic stats including Field Weighted Citation Impact (FWCI). It's like Scopus or Web of Science, but with a wider breadth of research outputs and an emphasis on humanities.

Google Scholar

Like OpenAlex, Google Scholar captures more grey literature in addition to traditional research outputs, including those that do not have DOIs like blog posts. For this reason, it tends to have the most complete record of research outputs, which in turn impacts a researcher's h-index. Additionally, you can see who is citing your work easily by clicking the "cited by" button under an individual work to see the types of articles and disciplines that use your research. If Google scholar is scraping research outputs it shouldn't include in an h-index, like supplementary materials, you can make an account and correct things (including adding grey literature).

SciVal

SciVal allows you to visualize your research performance, benchmark relative to peer institutions, identify and analyze emerging research trends, and create tailored reports. It's a service through Elsevier, so you may have institutional access. SciVal has some unique metrics compared to other bibliometric software including benchmarking institutions (so you can see how you perform against your university), as well as metrics per article, journal quality metrics, collaboration metrics, authorship metrics, and more. However, because it draws from Scopes, it has disciplinary and research output biases.

Collaboration metrics

Geographical Collaboration ⓘ

ⓘ Metric guidance + Add to Reporting Export ▾

International, national and institutional collaboration by Liboiron, Max in the selected year range.

Metric	Publication share	Scholarly Output	Citations
International collaboration	58.8%	10	462
Only national collaboration	5.9%	1	7
Only institutional collaboration	29.4%	5	129
Single authorship (no collaboration)	5.9%	1	82

SciVal collaboration metrics that show the geographical range of your co-authors, with citation counts for each type.

Authorship type	Scholarly Output	Authorship type share (%)	Field-Weighted Citation Impact	Outputs in Top 10% Cita...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> First author	4	23.5	1.23	1
<input type="checkbox"/> Last author	1	5.9	0.74	0
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Corresponding author <i>Data prior to June 2020 might be incomplete. Learn more</i>	6	35.3	2.07	2
<input type="checkbox"/> Co-author	9	52.9	4.19	5
<input type="checkbox"/> Single author	1	5.9	5.42	1
<input type="checkbox"/> First / Corresponding author	7	41.2	1.92	2
All publications	17	100	3.05	7

Journal quartiles

[Metric guidance](#) [+ Add to Reporting](#)

Share of publications per Journal quartile by CiteScore Percentile

Column chart Line chart

Incomplete year [?](#)

Quartiles	Publications	Publication share (%)
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Q1 (top 25%)	14	87.5
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Q2 (26% - 50%)	1	6.3
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Q3 (51% - 75%)	0	0.0
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Q4 (76% - 100%)	1	6.3

Scival bibliometric visualizations. Top: Breakdown of Field-weighted citations impacts and top journals by authorship type. This can be used to make arguments about the relative importance of solo- or first-authored papers versus team papers, particularly if you are making the case that team outputs are your strength and have the most impact.

Bottom: Journal ranking for an author's papers. Journals are ranked and then divided into four equal groups, with Q1 representing the top 25% (most prestigious) and Q4 representing the bottom 25% (least prestigious). This can be used to argue for the quality of your research, particularly in cases where a committee or outside evaluators aren't familiar with the top journals in your field.

Altmetrics

Altmetric is a system that tracks the online attention that research outputs receive, including mentions on social media, in news outlets, and other online sources. It's one of my (Max's) personal favourite bibliometric services because it extends more traditional citation-based metrics, especially for people who research on social and environmental issues.

Altmetrics analyzes any output with a DOI, and one of its unique metrics is the attention score, a weighted algorithm that reflects the number of mentions an article has had in the news, blogs, policy documents, patents, wikipedia, and social media as well as number of academic readers and citations (with a weighted bias towards news sources). It also provides an easy ranking of an output across all other outputs globally, within the same journal, from the same time to provide some nuance, and where in the world mentions are coming from. When I (Max) write external letters of review for promotion and tenure files, I find the comparison of research outputs especially useful for articulating merit. I've seen some CVs that include the Almetrics Attention score curl next to each paper, which might be particularly appropriate if you focus on research that gets a lot of media attention.

Finally, Altmetrics provides qualitative sentiment analysis to interpret the opinions expressed in social media mentions of an output. At the time of writing, this was in a beta phase.

An Almetrics Attention score for one paper. Each paper is evaluated separately rather than as a body of work. The circle with the number inside is the overall score, and I've seen these visualizations added to publication lines in CVs. This visualization shows the attention score over time, which can be used to make arguments about sustainability or key events.

Open Syllabus

Open Syllabus is an archive of syllabi. You can search for authors to see which texts are taught, how often, where, and in what disciplines. This may be a useful metric for people whose outputs differ significantly between what is taught and what is cited (this is the case for my own research!). Consider submitting your syllabi to the project.

www.opensyllabus.org/

RANK	TITLES	APPEARANCES	SCORE
1	Toxic Politics: Acting in a Permanently Polluted World Max Liboiron, Manuel Tironi, Nerea Calvillo <i>Social Studies of Science</i>	19	2
2	Redefining Pollution and Action: The Matter of Plastics Max Liboiron <i>Journal of Material Culture</i>	8	1

EMDV8017
Toxic: Environmental Pollution and Waste
Australian National University, 2020

ENGL 603
Media Archaeology
Concordia University, 2020

SHOW MORE

Open Syllabus analytics by author shows how often and in what courses specific texts are taught. You can extrapolate for the geographical location of courses based on universities to make an argument for international reputation.

Other tools & resources

- The **Metrics Toolkit** provides comprehensive and clear “information about research metrics across disciplines, including how each metric is calculated, where you can find it, and how each should (and should not) be applied.” It is useful for both applicants and reviewers: <https://metrics-toolkit.org>
- Deakin University's **Research Metrics help guide**, which includes metrics by discipline, non-traditional resource output impact metrics, and information on how different metrics are calculated: <https://deakin.libguides.com/research-metrics>
- **Lens** is a bibliographic service that is especially good for tracking impacts from patents, and impacts in industry and technology: [Lens.org](https://lens.org)
- **InCites** is similar to SciVal as a benchmarking tool that uses publications in the Web of Science catalogue. If you can't access SciVal, your library may have access to InCites.

Using evidence effectively

Numbers do not speak for themselves. If you provide an H-index, how is the committee supposed to interpret it? As a benchmark against all scholars in all disciplines (bad idea!), or against other scholars in your field at your level (better!), or in comparison to your own H-index at the time of your last promotion? Similarly, if your scholarship is characterized by becoming deeper and more nuanced, rather than through the proliferation of ever-more research outputs, what are the best ways to demonstrate that?

This section is organized according to the terms that often appear in promotion and tenure evaluation criteria with suggestions of how to use metrics to demonstrate them.

Development

Growth, sustainability, and maturity are three different ways to look at development.

- **Growth:** an increasing count of research outputs, number of collaborators, grant dollars, grant types, and graduate students.
- **Sustainability:** a consistent or gradually increasing number of outputs over time, showing a steadiness in growth or a commitment to stability for a lab or program. Some faculties have a written or unwritten standard of 2 or 3 peer-reviewed articles per year on average, for example. Others value a steady training program by showing a steady number of mentees or student funding.
- **Maturity:** Nuancing over time, including a diversification of outputs, an increase in prestige of publication venues, an increase in impacts, added complexity of outputs or audiences, etc, even if there is a decrease in counts. For example, one paper in Nature is worth more than three papers in predatory journals. Another common way to show maturity is a shift from internal, university grant funds to more competitive external funding, or from co-applicant status to principal investigator status on funds.

I used this graph to argue that a candidate demonstrated both maturity and growth in research outputs through the diversification of type of outputs to specific audiences. Moreover, each format required new skill development.

Impact: Citations

Citations are the gold standard bibliometric for approximating impact, based on the assumption that your impact on academia can be measured by how much your publications are cited. Of course, if your primary impact is not in academia or is not through peer-reviewed publications, you'll need to supplement this, but do not avoid it. It is the coin of the realm.

There are many metrics for citations, so choose ones that best describes your citation impact: h-index from a repository that best reflects your outputs (or you can calculate your own); Field Weighted Citation Impact (FWCI) from OpenAlex or SciVal; author impact beam plots from SciVal; and others, including field or funder-specific metrics.

Impact: Comparative excellence

Whether it is true or not, some things are automatically linked to impact, such as publishing in top journals. Other arguments for comparative excellence, like the analysis provided by Altmetric or SciVal, have to be created. Be sure to differentiate when you are comparing yourself to others in your field or globally (including professors that outrank you), versus when you are comparing yourself to others at the same rank, journal, discipline, or institution. Promotion and tenure are supposed to be rank-specific (i.e., comparing Assistant professors to Assistant professors), so if you are exceeding performance for your rank, be sure to provide that context ("meets and exceeds" is a great phrase for this).

An Altmetrics score for a candidate who had relatively few publications, but the publications were exceptional. I used comparative scores like this one to argue that they were performing above their rank, globally. Altmetric breaks down how each attention score is calculated, which I included in my evaluation.

Don't forget qualitative indications of comparative excellence, like awards. If you can find the success rate (number of nominations or applications versus number of awards) it can help make the case for excellence. Juried presentations, journal or funding rejection/acceptance rates, and similar activities that are inherently competitive can also be used.

Impact: Breadth of audience

Many bibliometrics show the disciplines for journal publications and in some cases readership that you can make the case for inter/disciplinary breadth (SciVal, Scopus, Web of Science, Altmetrics). Open Syllabus can provide evidence for student audiences that don't track in citation metrics. Almetrics also provides some breakdown for which media outlets and journalists are writing about your work.

Impact: Regional or international importance

You can show you are reaching an international audience by using mapped citations, viewership, news outlets, and downloads from various bibliographic sources and web analytics, if you have your own website or blog. SCOPUS, Web of Science, OpenAlex, and Almetrics all provide maps/country breakdowns.

However, if your research focus is best understood as regional because you are working with specific end users or audiences, be sure to explain that and use more regional metrics like the number or names of organizations, industries, and other end users who use or cite your work, or the standing of regional journals in which you publish.

Impact: End users

Metrics for impact on end users will vary greatly depending on your end user. See below for metrics for policy, industry, and professional end users.

Scopus, Web of Science, and [Lens.org](https://www.lens.org/) have metrics for citations of your work in patents and industry, while Altmetrics and PlumX metrics track mentions in policy. You can also use invitations to speak to these audiences as a measure of impact or relevance. Letters or testimonies from end users are also strong qualitative indicators.

Public reader reviews can be used from places like GoodReads, Amazon, and from more formal book reviews in journals.

Relevance

Relevance usually refers to the social applicability of your work to issues, problems, or needs outside of academia.

Showing relevance by use of your work by intended end-users is one way to show this. Scopus, Web of Science, and [Lens.org](#) have metrics for citations of your work in patents and industry, while Altmetrics, PlumX metrics track mentions in policy, for instance.

Media uptake is probably the most common and diffuse metric for showing relevance. The number of articles, number of articles over time, regional/national/international outlets, prestige of outlets, and your role in the media coverage (interviewee vs feature) are all ways to break down the relevance of media coverage.

Relatedly, you can use public lectures, viewership of films or podcasts, invitations to consult with speciality groups, or other measures of ways your work circulates outside of academia.

Finally, if you do community-based or partnered work, just listing those partnerships or invitations can point to relevance, though letters of support are better.

Prestige

Prestige is just a way to say “fancy venue”. It applies to journals, funders, conferences, publishers, and institutions. A publication in *Nature* is more prestigious than the same article published in *Regional Cell Biology Journal*, regardless of fit, number of citations, or other measures of impact.

Even if a venue is obviously prestigious to you, you'll want to use a metric to prove it. For journals, unless you are publishing in a globally top ranked journal (today, that is *Ca-A Cancer Journal for Clinicians* based on the [Scimago Journal & Country Rank](#)), you can use journal quartiles (which divide all journals with a journal impact factor into four groups) or the raw journal impact factor (though this requires some context for what counts as a good impact factor). SciVal provides a breakdown of all an author's publications by journal quartile.

You can also find third-party rankings for institutions, funders, awards, publishers, and other venues.

Reputation

Reputation is a way to talk about circulation *and* the character of your work. A good reputation indicates that not only are people talking about your work, but that they are saying it's good work.

Reputation can be indicated by invitations of any kind (to keynotes, presentations, collaborations, funding opportunities, media interviews), as it shows that your reputation preceded the invitation. You can also use third-party nominations, even if you didn't get what you were nominated for.

International standing

Many of the metrics discussed above can be mapped, including citations, readership, website views, collaborators, funders, media outlets, professional societies, presentation venues, courses that teach your syllabus, and more.

Interdisciplinarity

Most of the bibliometric services discussed above such as Web of Science, Scopus, OpenAlex, and even your own university library catalogue, will break down your publications by the journal discipline. You can create your own list of which disciplines teach your work using OpenSyllabus. Finally, though I'm not aware of bibliometric software that does this, you can outline the home disciplines of your co-authors, funding collaborators, or mentees.

Collaboration

You can highlight different aspects of collaboration: how large your teams are, how often you collaborate, how long you sustain collaborations, your roles in collaboration, with whom you collaborate (e.g., students, industry, government), and/or the characteristics of your collaborations (sustained, consensus-based, adaptable, interdisciplinary, diverse). Different metrics and measures will be required for what you want to highlight.

Some aspects of collaboration are readily measured by bibliometric software such as the nationality of co-authors (SciVal, Scopus, Web of Science) and your role in publication roles as corresponding author, anchor author, or lead author (SciVal). But you can also make your own, including the average number of co-authors per publication or grant, the total number of co-authors and team changes over time, the percentage of your publications that are co-authored, and the institutional, rank, gender, disciplinary, and geographical diversity of your co-authors.

Policy impacts

Sage Policy Profiles track how your research has been cited in international policy from governments, think tanks, and policymakers using your ORCID and name. You can also explain membership in on expert panels, expert witness testimony, or committees that guide policies, standards, or agendas

Professional impacts

Beyond citations, there are several ways to quantitatively and qualitatively describe your impacts on your field or profession:

- Contribution to professional association norms or guidelines.
- Citational analysis that shows your work circulating through specific types of citation (disciplines, uptake of a term or method, growth). Google Scholar, n-gram, Web of Science, and Scopus provide citational analyses of key terms.
- Academic reviews of your books (use quotes, the number of reviews, the fields of review through the journal [you can use Scopus or Web of Science for this]).
- Mentions in the acknowledgement sections of important books or reports.
- Awards or nominations.
- Keynotes or plenaries at professional associations.

Engagement

In academic settings, engagement is rarely defined, and the most common interpretation is simply attention from the public sphere.

Media coverage is one of the most common indicators of public engagement. Altmetrics tracks media mentions of articles with DOIs, but you can also search for your name or the name of a project in News-specific search engines and database repositories. Note the quality or prestige of media coverage; the difference between coverage and interviews; local versus national and international coverage.

If you have a website, you can use webviews and downloads of research products, and you can use the number of audience members at public presentations, community workshops, and other non-academic events. Other audience engagement can be captured in testimonials, royalty data, survey responses from events, letters of support from partners or end users, and social media likes/shares

Societal influence

Societal influence is more exacting than public engagement, and usually refers to a positive change in relationships between individuals, groups, and/or institutions. It might entail showing evidence of:

- Behaviour change due your work in the form of surveys, case studies, or testimonials;
- The amount of funding left in community or that goes towards infrastructure;
- A notable change in graduation rates or student demographics due to an intervention;
- Curriculum changes influenced by your work (changes in syllabi or test scores);
- Changes in discourse, language, or framing in a field or public setting (Voyant tools traces key words in uploaded texts and URLs <https://voyant-tools.org/>)
- Policy or industry uptake of your research (see above).

Conclusion and resources

These are only some of the ways to demonstrate, rather than just claim, that your research is impactful. Elsevier's "[Research Metrics Guidebook](#)" is an excellent resource for identifying measures of relevance--some, though not all, are on this list.

This report is meant to be used as part of a suite of IndigeLab Network resources on promotion and tenure, including "8 Maxims of Creating a Promotion and Tenure File," a promotion and tenure checklist, and guidelines for promotion and tenure for people who do community-based scholarship. We also provide examples of promotion and tenure files.

This list was last updated in the summer of 2025. Do you have a resource to add? Email the Coordinator at the IndigeLab Network. indigelabnetwork.com

Cite as: Liboiron, Max. (2025). *Research Impact in Focus: Tools and Strategies for Promotion and Tenure Documentation*. IndigeLab Network. DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.15814016](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15814016)

Examples

PUBLICATIONS

Books	Refereed Articles	Invited Articles	Book Chapters	Writing for Public Audiences	White Papers & Reports	Special Issue Co-Editor	Films	Total
2	38	20	14	~150	13	4	4	95
2%	41%	20%	14%	not included	14%	4%	4%	100%

Student and postdoc co-authors are underlined. Articles where author order was determined by consensus are marked with a *. * indicates open access. ★ indicates a publication award.

Summary in a CV with total counts and annotations for students, decision making for author order, open access, and publication awards. Note this is a CV for a full professor in an interdisciplinary field.

Graph showing the increasing scale of committee work as part of a larger argument about interdisciplinary expertise (much of the university committee work was for institution-wide grant evaluation) and national and international scope of reputation and impact.
PS- This is too much service for an Assistant professor; I was an administrator in 2018-19.

DISCIPLINES REPRESENTED BY CLEAR MEMBERS 2015-2019

Evidence of interdisciplinary lab membership. It's one thing to say, "my lab [or co-authors, or team] is interdisciplinary," and another to provide evidence of the breadth and diversity of that interdisciplinary. This graph was created with data from my CV on each lab member's home department/degree. This allowed me not only to demonstrate the breadth of knowledge translation happening in the lab, but also to show that I was serving the students in my cross-appointment departments (Geography and Sociology).

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